

ION-EXCHANGE REACTIONS WITH HETEROIONIC SYNTHETIC RESINS. PART II. ANION EXCHANGE

BY L. POCHHALI

Ion-exchange reactions with an anion-exchange resin, saturated with two different types of anions at different degrees of saturation, against a third anion have been studied by equilibrium method. Exchange of the more replaceable ion appears to increase and the less replaceable ion is suppressed; the interaction goes on increasing with the degree of saturation of the complementary ion. Of the three anions studied: Cl^- , NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} , when one of the saturating ions is SO_4^{2-} , the total exchange comes out to be antagonistic. The order of introduction of the SO_4^{2-} affects its release, showing that when it is introduced first it can take up exchange sites of higher binding energy. The structure of the strong base-anion exchange resin of polyamine type differs from that of sulphonated polystyrene resin, a strong acid cation exchanger.

In Part I (Pochhali, *this issue*, p. 521) the complications of ion-exchange reactions with heteroionic ion exchangers have been discussed. This present work deals with exchange reactions with an anion-exchange synthetic resin. It is mainly concerned with the study of the effect of the degree of saturation on the exchangeability of an anion from an anion-exchange resin, saturated with two different types of anions. The ions were exchanged by a third anion added at its symmetry concentration. Influence of the order of saturating the resin with the two anions on their exchangeability has been examined.

EXPERIMENTAL

As the anion exchanger, 'De-Acidite FF', a strong base synthetic resin, was used for the study. The nature of this resin and the method for its regeneration and purification have been described in an earlier publication (Pochhali, *this Journal*, 1960, 37 451).

The total ion-exchange capacity of the resin was determined in the following manner. A weighed quantity (3-4 g.) of the air-dried resin in the hydroxyl form was taken in a column and washed with distilled water till the effluent became colorless with phenolphthalein. A 5% solution of Na_2SO_4 was passed through the column and the effluent was collected in a litre volumetric flask up to the mark. The collected solution (100 c.c.) was titrated against a standard H_2SO_4 solution. The exchange capacity in m.e./g. of the air-dried resin was calculated from the titration value.

From the hydroxyl form of the resin, the following heteroionic resin salts were prepared :

The resin was saturated with the two types of anions at three different mutual degrees of saturation: 25-75, 50-50 and 75-25%. A weighed amount (~1 g.) of the OH-form of the resin was taken in a Jena glass bottle. A calculated amount of the first anion was introduced into the resin by adding its acid solution (HCl , HNO_3 or H_2SO_4) and keeping the mixture for 48 hours with occasional shaking. The second anion was then introduced similarly by adding the calculated volume of the corresponding standard acid solution so that the resin taken would now become completely saturated with the two anions. The mixture was again kept for 48 hours with occasional shaking in a mechanical shaker. The clear, practically neutral supernatant liquid was decanted and the resin was partially dried in air in the bottle at room temperature. A second set of resin salts was prepared by reversing the order of introduction of the two anions. To distinguish between the

two sets, we represent these as R-A-B and R-B-A; e.g. R-Cl-NO₃ represents the resin which is neutralised first with HCl and then with HNO₃ whereas R-NO₃-Cl represents the resin salt which is prepared by adding first HNO₃ and then HCl.

To these resin salts in bottles was added NaOH solution containing OH⁻ exactly equivalent to the amounts of the total exchangeable anions originally present in the resins. The total volumes of the solutions were kept constant at 50 c.c. The systems were then allowed to equilibrate on keeping for 48 hours with occasional shaking in a mechanical shaker. After equilibrium the clear solutions were analysed for estimating the two anions replaced.

The chloride was estimated volumetrically with a standard AgNO₃ solution using fluorescein as indicator, the nitrate by the modified Kjeldahl method using Devarda's alloy for reduction, and the sulphate gravimetrically as BaSO₄.

DISCUSSION

The results of the exchange experiments are shown graphically in Figs. 1-3. Here the amounts of each anion replaced are expressed as percentages of the total amount of anions originally present in the resins.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

From the replacement data of the anions from their pure forms of the resin against the same anion, OH⁻, the symmetry values are found to be as Cl-resin, 28.3; NO₃-resin, 21.6; SO₄-resin 16.7.

A comparison of the amounts of release for a particular anion from the two series of resin salts, e.g., R-A-B- and R-B-A, shows no difference between R-Cl-NO₃ and R-NO₃-Cl; the release of SO₄²⁻ from the salts in which it is introduced first is, however, slightly less than that where it was introduced last. This is true of Cl-SO₄ and NO₃-SO₄ series. The order of saturating the resin with SO₄²⁻ thus appears to affect its exchangeability. The SO₄²⁻ ion is held more strongly when it is introduced first.

The results for the total amount of anions replaced from the heteroionic resin salts at different degrees of saturation with respect to the two anions point to the fact that while in the Cl-NO₃

series, it is purely additive, in the Cl-SO_4 and $\text{NO}_3\text{-SO}_4$ series, the total amount of exchange is certainly antagonistic. In the Cl-NO_3 systems, though the Cl^- ion slightly suppresses the release of NO_3^- , its own release is enhanced slightly so that the resultant effect becomes additive. But in the case of Cl-SO_4 and $\text{NO}_3\text{-SO}_4$ systems, both Cl^- and NO_3^- suppress the release of SO_4^{2-} to such an extent that the total amount of anions replaced from their corresponding resin salts falls short of that demanded by additive behaviour, and hence antagonism is observed.

FIG. 3

The quantity of release of an individual anion is shown in Fig. 4 as the percentage of the amount of that particular ion present in the resin, instead of the total amounts of anions in the resin.

As in the case of heteroionic cation exchanger, here also a similar trend is observed in the percentage release with respect to the degree of saturation. The release of the more replaceable anion increases with its falling degree of saturation, but that of the less replaceable ion increases with its increasing degree of saturation. Thus in the Cl-NO_3 series, the replacement of Cl^- increases as its degree of saturation decreases, but that of NO_3^- decreases with its decreasing degree of saturation. But in the $\text{NO}_3\text{-SO}_4$ systems, NO_3^- behaves in the opposite way. With falling degree of saturation, the release of NO_3^- increases whereas that of SO_4^{2-} decreases. The same is the case with the Cl-SO_4 series.

Similar to the case of cation exchange from heteroionic systems, the exchange of the more exchangeable anion is also enhanced and that of the less exchangeable ion is suppressed in presence of each other. This mutual interionic effect is greater in the $\text{NO}_3\text{-SO}_4$ systems than in the Cl-SO_4 systems. At corresponding degree of saturation NO_3^- suppresses more effectively the release of SO_4^{2-} than the Cl^- ion.

The variation of the selectivity coefficient of OH^- against the other two anions present in the resin (K_{A+B}^{CH}) with their degrees of saturation is shown in Fig. 5. As with the resin salts,

R-A-B and R-B-A, the values of the selectivity coefficient differ very slightly, the mean of the two values has been taken.

FIG. 4

FIG. 5

The variation in the values of the selectivity coefficient with the degree of saturation is found to be gradual in R-Cl-NO₃ like the cation-exchange resin, 'Zeo Karb 225' (this issue, p. 521). But where one of the saturating ions is SO₄²⁻, K_{A+B}^{OH-} has a tendency of having a minimum value at a certain degree of saturation, which is actually realised in the case of R-NO₃-SO₄. This also shows that SO₄²⁻ can enter positions of higher binding energy in the exchange resin and is released with more difficulty than monovalent anions like Cl⁻ and NO₃⁻.

The observations recorded here indicate that the structure of the polyamine resins like 'De-Acedite FF' differs from that of the cation-exchange resins like 'Zeo-Karb 225'. In the latter all the exchange sites are identical whereas in this anion-exchange resin there are some exchange sites, which are quite different from others regarding their binding energy for ions.

The author's grateful thanks are due to Prof. S. N. Mukherjee, D.Sc., Head of the Department of Chemistry, Jadavpur University and to Prof. S. K. Mukherjee, D.Sc., Unesco Consultant, Universitas Svmatra, Utara, Indonesia, for their kind and helpful suggestions and encouragement.